

Interactions among antithrombotic agents in acute coronary syndrome: association with bleeding and hospital length of stay

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Received 2 July 2025 ♦ Accepted 4 August 2025 ♦ Published 12 September 2025

Citation: Nurdiana S, Kurniati NF, Dewi TI, Zazuli Z (2025) Interactions among antithrombotic agents in acute coronary syndrome: association with bleeding and hospital length of stay. *Pharmacia* 72: 1–8. <https://doi.org/10.3897/pharmacia.72.e163748>

Abstract

Acute coronary syndrome management requires antiplatelets and anticoagulants to prevent thrombus formation. However, concurrent use may lead to drug interactions and harmful effects – such as bleeding – that can impact the patient's treatment process, including the length of stay (LOS). This study aimed to analyze potential and actual drug interactions among antithrombotic agents and their association with LOS. This retrospective study was conducted using electronic medical records and laboratory results from patients during the period October 2024–March 2025. The inclusion criteria were hospitalized patients receiving antithrombotic agents. A total of 176 patients were included using a consecutive sampling method. Drug interactions were analyzed using Micromedex. Bleeding was evaluated using hemoglobin levels and clinical signs based on BARC criteria. Bleeding was observed in 14 patients, of whom 57.14% received three or more antithrombotic agents. The most common potential pharmacodynamic interaction occurred between aspirin and clopidogrel. The median LOS was 4 days (IQR 4), and the median number of potential pharmacodynamic interactions was 3 (IQR 3). The number of drugs and LOS were significantly higher in the bleeding group ($p < 0.05$). The number of drugs and the type of ACS were significant factors influencing LOS.

Keywords

antithrombotic, bleeding, drug interaction, length of stay

Introduction

Acute coronary syndrome (ACS) is one of the clinical manifestations of coronary heart disease resulting from a sudden decrease in blood flow to the heart. This decrease is caused by an occlusion following the rupture of an unstable atherosclerotic plaque. Atherosclerosis arises from endothelial dysfunction and the accumulation of oxidized low-density lipoprotein (LDL), triggering a series of inflammatory processes and plaque formation. Plaques with

a thin fibrous cap and a large necrotic core may be unstable and rupture, causing a cascade of coagulation and thrombus formation (Jebari-Benslaiman et al. 2022). The resulting decrease in blood flow triggers ischemia and can lead to heart muscle cell death or infarction. This condition is known as myocardial infarction (MI) or heart attack (Didomenico et al. 2023).

Management of ACS aims to rapidly restore coronary blood flow and prevent recurrent ischemic events. Antiplatelet therapy is a fundamental component in the man-

agement of ACS. Dual antiplatelet therapy (DAPT), which combines aspirin with a P2Y₁₂ inhibitor such as clopidogrel, is used for both short-term and long-term therapy, particularly in patients undergoing interventions such as stenting via percutaneous coronary intervention (PCI). In addition to antiplatelet agents, patients with ACS often use anticoagulants – particularly those with atrial fibrillation or a history of venous thromboembolism and those undergoing PCI – to prevent stent thrombosis (Onwordi et al. 2018). While the concurrent use of multiple drugs that prevent blood clotting is important for reducing the risk of recurrent cardiovascular events, it may also lead to pharmacodynamic drug interactions that increase the risk of bleeding.

A drug interaction is defined as a change in the effect of a drug caused by the presence of another chemical compound in the body at the same time. These compounds may include drugs, food, herbal medicines, or other substances that affect the drug's efficacy (Baxter 2010). The occurrence of drug interactions can result in adverse effects, such as bleeding. Such effects may lead to hospitalization, rehospitalization, and increased length of stay. The length of stay refers to the duration a patient spends in a hospital or healthcare facility, from admission to discharge (Stone et al. 2022). An increase in the length of hospitalization may elevate healthcare expenditure, the risk of nosocomial infections, and psychological burden – as well as reduce the patient's physical mobility (Hirani et al. 2025). The incidence of pharmacodynamic drug interactions involving antithrombotic agents needs to be monitored carefully to minimize adverse side effects in patients. Actual pharmacodynamic interactions in patients with ACS are still not widely studied, especially in Indonesia. This study aims to identify potential and actual pharmacodynamic drug interactions – specifically involving antithrombotic agents – and analyze their effect on the length of hospitalization.

Materials and methods

The study was conducted retrospectively using secondary patient data obtained through electronic medical records and laboratory results.

Participants

This research obtained ethical approval from the Padjadjaran University Research Ethics Commission (No. 266/UN6.KEP/EC/2025). The study was conducted at Hasan Sadikin Hospital, Bandung. Samples were selected using a consecutive sampling method based on inclusion criteria. Inclusion criteria in this study were patients diagnosed with acute coronary syndrome (STEMI or NSTEMI), hospitalized between October 2024 and March 2025, and who received at least two antithrombotic agents during admission. Exclusion criteria were patients whose medical records were incomplete or inaccessible, who received only one antithrombotic agent, or who passed away within the initial 24-hour period following admission.

Data collection

Hemoglobin values and clinical events were used to assess bleeding events, based on the Bleeding Academic Research Consortium (BARC) classification. Clinical signs were obtained from narrative notes in the physician's documentation. Medicines used during hospitalization were examined through drug use records and analyzed using Micromedex to identify potential drug interactions.

Statistical analysis

The number of samples was determined using the bivariate normal model formula, with an alpha value of 0.05, a beta value of 0.2, and a correlation coefficient value from previous research of 0.22. Therefore, the minimum number of participants was 160. In this study, 176 medical records met the inclusion criteria and were included as research samples.

Based on normality testing using the Kolmogorov–Smirnov test, it was found that the data distribution was not normal; therefore, non-parametric tests were used. Data are shown as median (interquartile range, IQR). Continuous variables – such as age, length of stay, number of comorbidities, number of drugs, number of antithrombotic agents, and number of potential pharmacodynamic interactions – were analyzed using the Mann–Whitney U test. Categorical variables – such as gender and type of ACS – were analyzed using Fisher's exact test and the Chi-square test. A correlation test between variables was performed using the Spearman rank test. Logistic regression was performed to assess which variables influenced the incidence of bleeding. Multiple linear regression was performed to evaluate the variables that influenced the length of stay. Variables included in the multivariate regression analysis were those with a p-value < 0.2 in the bivariate analysis. Statistical analysis was performed using Minitab Statistical Software 22. The results of the analysis were considered statistically significant if the p-value < 0.05.

Results

During the study period, there were 198 patients whose medical records could be accessed. However, 22 patients did not meet the inclusion criteria because their data were incomplete, they received only one antithrombotic drug, they died, or they had multiple admissions. Thus, the total number of patients who met the inclusion criteria was 176.

A total of 148 patients were male, and 28 patients were female. Their ages ranged from 25 to 90 years, with a median of 56 years (IQR 15). The length of stay had a median value of 4 days (IQR 4). ST-elevation myocardial infarction (STEMI) was the predominant diagnosis (69.32%). The number of comorbidities per patient had a median value of 2. Hypertension, diabetes mellitus, and acute kidney injury were the most common comorbidities in this study.

Figure 1. Flowchart of study sample selection.

The number of drugs prescribed per patient during hospitalization ranged from 8 to 61 (median = 17). The median number of antithrombotic agents per patient was 3 (IQR 1). In this study, 14 patients (7.95%) showed signs of bleeding – both clinically and based on laboratory results. The most common clinical signs of bleeding observed were hematuria and gastrointestinal (GI) bleeding.

A total of 742 potential pharmacodynamic interactions were identified. Table 2 shows the 10 most frequent potential interactions. For the complete list of drug interactions, see Supplementary file 1: List of drug interactions. The most frequent combinations were aspirin–clopidogrel (14.29%) and aspirin–ticagrelor (13.48%).

Comparative analysis in Table 3 showed that the length of stay and the number of drugs received by patients in the bleeding group were significantly different from those in the non-bleeding group. The bleeding group had a longer hospital stay (5 days vs 3 days) and a higher number of medications (23 drugs vs 16 drugs). The results of the multivariate analysis with logistic regression in Table 4 show that none of the variables had a significant effect on the incidence of bleeding ($p > 0.05$).

Table 5 shows the results of the bivariate and multivariate analyses related to the factors associated with the length of hospital stay. Multiple linear regression analysis

showed that the type of ACS diagnosis and the number of drugs were the variables that had a significant influence on length of stay. Patients with a diagnosis of STEMI had a shorter hospital stay than patients with a diagnosis of NSTEMI. The number of drugs administered to patients had a strong correlation with the length of hospital stay.

Discussion

This study examined the association between pharmacodynamic interactions among antithrombotic agents and clinical outcomes – especially bleeding occurrence and length of hospital stay – in patients with acute coronary syndrome (ACS). The findings highlight the high prevalence of potential pharmacodynamic interactions involving commonly used antiplatelet and anticoagulant combinations.

In this study, the number of male patients was higher than the number of female patients. These results are consistent with those from the acute coronary syndrome registries in Indonesia and Malaysia (Lu et al. 2014; Juzar et al. 2022). Unhealthy lifestyles, such as smoking and alcohol consumption, as well as hormonal differences – especially estrogen – lead to an increased risk of ACS in men (Aminuddin et al. 2023).

Table 1. Baseline characteristics of the study population.

Variables	Category	Frequency	Percentage
Gender	Male	148	84.09%
	Female	28	15.91%
Age (years)	<45	18	10.23%
	45–60	106	60.23%
	61–76	43	24.43%
	>76	9	5.11%
Type of ACS	STEMI	122	69.32%
	NSTEMI	54	30.86%
Length of stay (days)	≤ 4	117	66.47%
	> 4	59	33.53%
Number of drugs per patient	< 10	13	7.38%
	10–20	101	57.38%
	> 20	62	35.24%
Number of antithrombotic agents	≤ 3 drugs	94	53.4%
	> 3 drugs	82	46.6%
Number of potential pharmacodynamic interaction	≤ 3	96	54.55%
	> 3	80	45.45%
Number of comorbidity	≤ 2	90	51.13%
	> 2	86	48.87%
Types of comorbidity	Hypertension	85	48.3%
	DM	62	35.23%
	AKI	37	21.02%
	CHF	27	15.34%
	Ischemic cardiomyopathy	12	6.8%
	COPD	9	5.1%
	Atrioventricular block	8	4.5%

Abbreviations: ACS = acute coronary syndrome; AKI = acute kidney injury; CHF = congestive heart failure; COPD = chronic obstructive pulmonary disease; DM = diabetes mellitus; NSTEMI = non-ST elevation myocardial infarction; STEMI = ST elevation myocardial infarction.

Table 2. Most frequent potential pharmacodynamic interactions (N = 742).

No	Potential drug interaction	n	%
1	Aspirin–clopidogrel	106	14.29%
2	Aspirin–ticagrelor	100	13.48%
3	Aspirin–heparin	91	12.26%
4	Aspirin–enoxaparin	68	9.16%
5	Clopidogrel–heparin	59	7.95%
6	Heparin–ticagrelor	44	5.93%
7	Aspirin–fondaparinux	39	5.26%
8	Clopidogrel–enoxaparin	36	4.85%
9	Clopidogrel–ticagrelor	33	4.45%
10	Heparin–enoxaparin	31	4.18%

A total of 48.3% of patients in this study were diagnosed with hypertension as an additional condition. This is consistent with another study showing that more than 50% of ACS patients have hypertension (Lin et al. 2013). Hypertension is a major risk factor for ACS, triggering atherogenesis and the development of unstable or vulner-

able plaques, which can lead to thrombosis or vessel occlusion (Picariello et al. 2011). Diabetes mellitus is also a risk factor that can cause and exacerbate conditions in patients with ACS. Hyperglycemia causes platelets to exhibit signal transduction dysregulation, which leads to excessive activation and aggregation of platelets, as well as activation of thrombin (Verma and Kalra 2023). In this study, 35.22% of patients had diabetes mellitus (DM), which is consistent with previous study findings (Stampouloglou et al. 2023). The use of contrast agents in PCI procedures can cause contrast-induced AKI. A total of 21.02% of patients experienced acute kidney injury (AKI).

The most common potential drug interactions in this study were those between antiplatelet agents, such as aspirin, and P2Y12 inhibitors, including clopidogrel and ticagrelor. These combinations are consistent with dual antiplatelet therapy (DAPT), which is commonly recommended for managing acute coronary syndrome. This aligns with previous research on cardiothoracic ICU patients in China (Wang et al. 2022). Based on current guidelines, ticagrelor is the first-choice P2Y12 agent due to its greater potency, with clopidogrel used as an alternative when contraindications exist (Byrne et al. 2023). A study on drug interactions in hospitalized patients with heart disease found that the antiplatelet group had the highest number of potential drug interactions (79.6%), followed by the anticoagulant group, which accounted for 20% of the total interacting drugs (Kalash et al. 2023).

The interaction between antithrombotic drugs is a pharmacodynamic interaction – an interaction that occurs at the receptor or drug target level when drugs with similar or opposing pharmacological effects are administered simultaneously (Zheng 2020). Antithrombotic drugs – including antiplatelets, anticoagulants, and fibrinolytics – inhibit the hemostasis process through different pathways. When these three classes are used together, the hemostasis process is inhibited from all sides, thereby increasing the risk of bleeding. The interaction among these three classes has an additive effect, meaning that the overall effect of the drug combination is the sum of the pharmacological effects of each individual drug (Niu et al. 2019). According to Micromedex, the severity of all drug interactions identified in this study was classified as major – interactions that can have life-threatening consequences and/or require intervention to minimize or prevent serious side effects. Therefore, if concomitant use is necessary based on a risk–benefit assessment, close monitoring of the patient is required, especially for those at high risk.

The analysis of gender and age variables revealed no significant differences between the groups that experienced bleeding and those that did not. These results suggest that bleeding is not associated with gender or age. However, previous research showed a significant difference in age between patients who experienced bleeding and those who did not (Sun et al. 2022). That study's analysis of additional variables – including renal function and hemodynamic status – may explain the discrepancy.

Table 3. Comparison between bleeding and non-bleeding groups.

Variable	Category	Bleeding group (n = 14)	Non-bleeding group (n = 162)	p-value
Gender, n (%)	Male	13 (92.85%)	135 (83.3%)	0.701
	Female	1 (7.15%)	27 (16.7%)	
Type of ACS, n (%)	STEMI	10 (71.42%)	112 (69.14%)	1
	NSTEMI	4 (28.58%)	50 (30.86%)	
Age (years)	Median (IQR)	56.5 (16)	55.5 (16)	0.648
LOS (days)	Median (IQR)	5 (3.5)	3 (3)	0.031*
Number of drugs per patient	Median (IQR)	23 (15.25)	16 (10)	0.001*
Number of antithrombotic agents	Median (IQR)	4 (2)	3 (1)	0.148
	>3 drugs	8 (57.14%)	74 (45.68%)	0.409
	≤3 drugs	6 (42.86%)	88 (54.32%)	
Number of potential drug interactions	Median (IQR)	5.5 (6.25)	3 (3)	0.275
Number of comorbidities	Median (IQR)	3 (3.5)	2 (3)	0.527
Hemoglobin (g/dL)	Initial	13.55	14	0.812
	Final	14.5	13.7	0.785
	ΔHb	-1.2	-0.5	0.099

Abbreviations: ACS = acute coronary syndrome; Hb = hemoglobin; IQR = interquartile range; LOS = length of stay; NSTEMI = non-ST elevation myocardial infarction; STEMI = ST elevation myocardial infarction.

Table 4. Multivariate analysis of factors associated with bleeding.

Variable	OR	95% CI	p-value
Length of stay	1.1188	0.9205; 1.3599	0.259
Number of drugs	1.0295	0.9481; 1.1178	0.489
Number of antithrombotic agents	1.2312	0.6576; 2.3050	0.516

CI: confidence interval; OR: odd ratio

The median length of stay was significantly greater in the bleeding group than in the non-bleeding group (5 days vs 3 days, $p < 0.05$). These results suggest that bleeding is associated with longer hospital stays. A previous study showed similar results, reporting that the length of stay was longer for patients who experienced major bleeding than for those who did not (12 days vs 9 days) (Sun et al. 2022). Patients experiencing drug side effects – such as bleeding – require further observation and treatment, which can extend the length of stay.

Analysis of the primary diagnosis revealed no significant correlation between ACS type and bleeding incidence. Median hemoglobin values at baseline and at the end of hospitalization showed no significant differences between the two groups. Other parameters – such as INR, aPTT, and PT – were not analyzed because they were not routinely measured.

In this study, patients received an average of 17 drugs, three of which were antithrombotic agents. According to the guidelines, ACS patients typically receive two types of antiplatelet medications (DAPT) and one anticoagulant during hospitalization – particularly those undergoing invasive procedures such as PCI (Rao et al. 2025). A previous study on PCI patients in Japan showed that the median number of antithrombotic agents used was two (Yamamoto et al. 2024). Previous multicenter studies have shown that 98% of ACS patients used ≥ 5 drugs and 40% received ≥ 10 drugs (Turner et al. 2020). The number of drugs in the bleeding group was

greater than in the non-bleeding group. This finding aligns with prior studies indicating that polypharmacy is associated with an elevated risk of both major and clinically relevant non-major bleeding (Leiss et al. 2015; Gallagher et al. 2020). A study by Yamamoto et al. (2024) showed that the 5-year cumulative incidence of primary bleeding events increased gradually with the number of medications used.

The number of potential pharmacodynamic interactions was greater in the bleeding group than in the non-bleeding group. However, the statistical results did not show a significant difference. Previous studies have demonstrated an association between the number of potential drug interactions – especially those related to anticoagulant use – and bleeding events (Lee et al. 2020). Although not statistically significant, this could still serve as a basis for assessing increased bleeding risk in patients with a higher number of drug interactions. Therefore, closer monitoring of patients with potential drug interactions is necessary. Clinical pharmacy plays an important role in risk assessment, education, and collaboration with other healthcare professionals in patient care – especially for high-risk patients.

Bivariate analysis revealed a significant difference in length of hospitalization between patients diagnosed with STEMI and those with NSTEMI. Multivariate analysis showed consistent results. Patients with a primary diagnosis of NSTEMI had a longer length of stay. Previous studies have reported similar findings – NSTEMI patients tend to be older, have more extensive coronary artery disease, and have more comorbidities than STEMI patients (Puymirat et al. 2017).

Analysis of the age variable showed a weak association with length of stay. Previous studies have suggested that older age is associated with increased length of stay in patients with ACS. As age increases, physiological function declines – causing greater complexity in disease management that requires evaluation and prolonged hospitalization (Tang et al. 2024). Length of stay also showed a

Table 5. Analysis of factors that are associated with length of stay.

Variable	LOS, days (Median (IQR))	Bivariate analysis			Multivariate analysis		
		ρ	Interpretation	p-value	B	95% CI	p-value
Gender				0.550			
Male	4 (4)						
Female	3.5 (3)						
Type of ACS				0.002*		(-0.1462;-0.0266)	0.005*
NSTEMI	5 (4)				Ref		
STEMI	3 (3)				-0.0864		
Bleeding				0.031*		(-0.0634;0.1421)	0.451
No	3 (3)				Ref		
Yes	5 (3.5)				0.0394		
Age		0.189	Very weak	0.012*	0.00039	(-0.00211;0.0029)	0.757
Number of Comorbid		0.413	Moderate	0.000*	0.01781	(-0.00084;0.03645)	0.061
Number of drugs		0.657	Strong	0.000*	0.01765	(0.01336;0.02194)	0.000*
Number of potential pharmacodynamic interactions		0.248	Weak	0.001*	0.00386	(-0.00648;0.01457)	0.477
Number of antithrombotic drugs		0.267	Weak	0.000*			

Abbreviations: ρ = Spearman's rank correlation coefficient; ACS = acute coronary syndrome; B = regression coefficient; LOS = length of stay.

moderate association with the number of comorbidities. A systematic review showed that ACS patients with multimorbidity had a longer length of stay (Breen et al. 2020).

The number of drugs was strongly associated with length of hospitalization. Patients with more complex disease states requiring more drugs usually undergo longer hospitalizations. However, receiving multiple medications also increases the risk of adverse events and drug interactions, which may further prolong hospitalization. This analysis cannot infer causality – it only examines the relationship between variables.

Analysis of length of stay in the bleeding and non-bleeding groups showed a significant difference ($p = 0.031$). However, after correcting for age, number of drugs, type of ACS diagnosis, number of comorbidities, and number of bleeding-related drugs, bleeding was no longer an independent predictor of length of stay.

This study has the advantage of not only relying on potential drug interactions based on literature or databases but also analyzing actual drug interactions occurring in patients during treatment. The limitation of this study is that it was conducted retrospectively – so there is a possibility of incomplete information regarding bleeding events, as no direct observation was made. Nevertheless, the results of this study still provide insight into the incidence of bleeding as an actual drug interaction occurring in patients with ACS. Future studies are expected to be conducted prospectively to observe the effects of drug interactions directly.

Conclusion

Potential pharmacodynamic interactions between anti-thrombotic medications were shown to be highly prevalent in hospitalized acute coronary syndrome (ACS) patients. Bleeding can result from these interactions, and in this

study, it occurred in 14 patients (7.8% of the total sample). The median length of stay for those patients was significantly longer than for those who did not experience bleeding, and 57% of them received three or more antithrombotic agents. Medication regimens must be closely monitored in order to reduce the risk of bleeding and prolonged hospital stays.

Acknowledgments

The authors would like to express their gratitude to the Pharmacy and Medical Records Departments of Hasan Sadikin Hospital (RSHS) Bandung for their assistance in providing access to the patient data utilized in this study.

Additional information

Conflict of interest

The authors have declared that no competing interests exist.

Ethical statements

The authors declared that no clinical trials were used in the present study.

The authors declared that no experiments on humans or human tissues were performed for the present study.

The authors declared that no informed consent was obtained from the humans, donors, or donors' representatives participating in the study.

The authors declared that no experiments on animals were performed for the present study.

The authors declared that no commercially available immortalized human or animal cell lines were used in the present study.

Use of AI

No use of AI was reported.

Funding

This study was funded by the 2025 Research, Community Service, and Innovation (PPMI 2025) Program, School of Pharmacy, Institut Teknologi Bandung (grant number 26D/IT1.C10/SK-KU/2025).

Author contributions

All authors have contributed equally.

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Data availability

All of the data that support the findings of this study are available in the main text or Supplementary Information.

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Supplementary material 1

List of drug interactions

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Data type: xlsx

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Link: <https://doi.org/10.3897/pharmacia.72.e163748.suppl1>